

A STUDY ON HIGH TEMPERATURE STABILITY OF NEW-TYPED MULTILAYER INSULATION

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SUMMARY

The new-typed MLI comprised of alumina silicate fiber-papers, high temperature adhesive, hydrophobic silica aerogels granules and potassium hexatitanate ($K_2Ti_6O_{13}$) whisker was prepared by felting process. The two samples by adding aerogels and $K_2Ti_6O_{13}$ whisker respectively were heat treatment for 100 h and 100 times at intervals of 1 h at 800 °C and 1000 °C. The microstructure, phase transfer and thermal conductivity of the two kinds of samples were characterized by SEM, XRD and calorimeter determination. These MLI samples took on less mass loss. The serious sinter of adhesive layers and decomposition of whiskers resulted in thermal conductivity increase.

Keywords: multilayer insulation; potassium hexatitanate whisker; thermal conductivity; high temperature stability; aerogels

INTRODUCTION

Multilayer insulation (MLI) consists of reflecting screen of high reflective index and spacers of low thermal conductivity alternately, whose insulation ability is better than conventional insulations. Metal foil is usually used as reflecting screen in high temperature station and resisting heat flow into the inside structure [1-3]. The MLI has been used in lots of fields, especially in space vehicles. For example, MLI of Hermes space shuttle was a light insulation system composed of fiber insulation mats partitioned off from reflecting screen [4]. MLI used on liquid oxygen tank of the Delta Clipper airship of McDonnell Douglas in America was composed of alumina felt and radiation shield foil [5].

In our research, MLI was produced by adding silica aerogels into high temperature adhesive [6]. As we know, thermal radiation is the main factor for heat transfer in high temperature environment and the radiative energy mainly concentrates the wavelength region between 2 and 8 μm [7]. But silica aerogels show the low adsorption between these regions, which is responsible for strong increase in thermal conductivity in high temperature. In this paper, a new-typed MLI was produced by adding potassium hexatitanate ($K_2Ti_6O_{13}$) whisker into MLI in order to reduce its heat conductivity, especially its radiative conductivity. This new-typed MLI underwent long time and recurrent heat treatments at 800 °C and 1000 °C for investigating its degeneration of insulated effect.

EXPERIMENTAL

The new-typed MLI comprised of alumina silicate fiber-papers, hydrophobic silica aerogels granules and $K_2Ti_6O_{13}$ whisker as a kind of fillings is developed by felting process. At first, appropriate silica aerogels particles were filtered and dispersed homogeneously in high temperature adhesive which was diluted by absolute ethanol. Then $K_2Ti_6O_{13}$ whisker was added into this mixture as appropriate proportion. The mixture was stirred until no dry powder and no excess wetting agent existed. High temperature adhesive taking on high viscosity was obtained after sufficient stirring. This new adhesive was spread equably on the surface of fiber paper keeping coherence among fiber layers. In order to avoid high density, the layers with adding $K_2Ti_6O_{13}$ whisker only had been coated five times. The rest layers only adding aerogels particles were coated as above according to the practical needed layer numbers. In order to reduce the contact between thermal resource and hot side of sample, quartz fiber sheet of 1×1 mm mesh was stuck on the exterior surface of sample. When the MLI sample was finished, it was kept in ventilating cabinet for 48 hours in order to get rid of organic solvent and reduce the shrinkage of adhesive layers. Then the MLI sample was dried and solidified in drying oven at $60^\circ C$ for another 48 hours. At last, the sample was sintered at $800^\circ C$ for 3 hours to remove organic components in it.

According to the above method, two kinds of MLI samples were prepared by mixing silica aerogels only (JX0) and silica aerogels and $K_2Ti_6O_{13}$ whisker together (JX1) into high temperature adhesive respectively. These two samples were heat treatment for 100 h and 100 times at intervals of 1 h at $800^\circ C$ and $1000^\circ C$.

Scanning electron micrographs (SEM) were obtained on specimens using a FEI Sirion (Holand) instrument. The samples were analyzed with 15 kV or 20 kV beam voltage for a sufficiently short time to limit charging of the fractured samples sputtered with gold. X-ray powder diffraction analysis was performed using a Dmax-rB diffractometer. Thermal conductivity test, i.e. calorimeter determination of thermal conductivity, is measured according to Chinese standard YB/T 4130-2005.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 The mass change curves and fitting of JX0 and JX1 at $800^\circ C$ heat treatment for 100 times in 1 h

The appearance of MLI is not changed after long time and many times recurrent heat

treatment. The bonding among fiber-papers firms and has no obvious cracks and abscission. Because of the action of sintering for long time, the silica and alumina are sintered obviously between fiber-papers and adhesive layer and the associated strength is increased in some degree. Figure 1 is the mass change curves of JX0 and JX1 at 800 °C heat treatment for 100 times in 1 h respectively. The fitting curves and equations are also shown in the figure 1. The mass of these two samples both decrease in the course of heat treatment all the time. And the mass loss degree is quick at the beginning of heat treatment, which comes from the volatilization and decomposing of water and organic solvent. The total mass loss is 1.05% and 1.94% for JX0 and JX1 respectively.

As we know, when the inorganic material is heated for long time especially in high temperature, the sinter will occur. Figure 2 is the adhesive layer SEM of JX0 and JX1 at 1000 °C for 100 h. The silica aerogels congregating around the adhesive particles were sintered and increase in size. Because of matter flow from the finest solid arms of the cluster to the locations where the solid density is the highest, the cluster shrinks [8]. The same sinter phenomenon also takes place among the adhesive particles. The result of shrinkage is that the materials become more compact and the porous net structure of aerogels is destroyed or weakened. The sinter was accelerated by adding $K_2Ti_6O_{13}$ whiskers into adhesive as shown in Figure 2 (b). The spherical aerogels and adhesive particles disappeared and were sintered to form compact sheet structure in which there was no the porous net structure. The porous structure of adhesive layer, however, was reserved because the fiber-papers bounded its shrinkage in the course of long time sintering action. There are more micro-pores than the sinter before, which is much nano-pores originating from aerogels. The long time heat treatment changes the porous structure of adhesive, which is a disadvantage for solid thermal conductivity.

Figure 2 Adhesive layer SEM of JX0 and JX1 at 1000 °C for heat treatment 100 h

Figure 3 shows the adhesive XRD patterns for sample JX0 and JX1 long-time-heat-treated at different temperatures. It could be seen that the adhesive of JX0 was amorphous at 800 °C and some andalusite phase appeared at 1000 °C which comes from alumina and silica in adhesive and silica aerogels. Because the content of alumina is less, the alumina diffractive peak is concealed by silica amorphous ones at 800 °C. The adhesive of sample JX1 takes on crystalline phase, i.e. TiO_2 anatase and SiO_2 cristobalite phase, after long time heat treatment at 800 °C. The SiO_2 cristobalite phase

comes from silica aerogels which is amorphous phase after short time heat treatment at 800 °C. It can be concluded that the phase transformation for silica aerogels might occur from amorphous phase to crystalline state at 800 °C because of the adding of $K_2Ti_6O_{13}$ whiskers [9]. The decomposed whisker exhibits TiO_2 anatase phase at 800 °C and main TiO_2 rutile one at 1000 °C after long time heat treatment.

Figure 3 The adhesive XRD patterns for sample JX0 and JX1 long-time-heat-treated at different temperatures

Figure 4 Thermal conductivities of JX0 and JX1 at different temperature on heat surface

Figure 4 is thermal conductivities of JX0 and JX1 at different temperature on heat surface. When JX0 and JX1 were not heated for long time, JX1 has lower thermal conductivity than the one of JX0. $K_2Ti_6O_{13}$ whisker has a high-reflection index and negative temperature thermal conductivity [10]. Radiative energy could be reflected by the additive of $K_2Ti_6O_{13}$ whisker in high temperature environment, i.e. more absorbing energy could be blocked. But there is an obviously increase after long time heat treatment especially at 1000 °C. As we know, the additive of $K_2Ti_6O_{13}$ leads to a strong increase of the specific extinction even if it decomposes to different TiO_2 phases at high temperature and will decrease the radiative thermal conductivity [11]. But the intense sinter of adhesive layer and the degeneration of fiber-paper are the other main reasons for the increase of solid thermal conductivity. In addition, the additive of $K_2Ti_6O_{13}$ whisker results in the decrease of phase transfer temperature of silica aerogels, which is another reason to increase the thermal conductivity of JX1. And from the result of thermal conductivity experiment, the latter factor is the main influencing reason resulting in thermal conductivity increase.

CONCLUSION

New-typed multilayer insulation (MLI) was prepared by adding silica aerogels powder and $K_2Ti_6O_{13}$ whiskers into high temperature adhesive. The total mass loss is 1.05% and 1.94% for JX0 and JX1 respectively after 100 times heat treatment at 800 °C at intervals of 1 hour. The thermal conductivities of all kinds of samples increased because of the serious sinter of modified adhesive. The additive of $K_2Ti_6O_{13}$ whisker resulting in the decrease of phase transfer temperature of silica aerogels and solid adhesive layer sintering is the main reason of thermal conductivity increase.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No.50802020) and Development Program for Outstanding Young Teachers in Harbin Institute of Technology (HITQNJS.2007.003).

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